

ISic3201

I.Sicily inscription 3201

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone (?)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance

Modione (?)

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Malibu CA, USA, J. Paul Getty Museum, inventory 80 AA 42

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI336392

1. Λατίνο⁻ η έμί,
2. τὸ Ἰε⁻γίνο⁻ έμί.
3. vacat
- 4.

Edition: PHI337020

1. Λατῖνο^h ²⁶Λατῖνος²⁶ έμί,
2. τὸ Ἰε⁻γίνο⁻ έμί.
- 3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284888

EDCS 64400286

PHI 336392

PHI 337020

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 53.1033

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 49.1342

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